

Synthesis of 5,6,8,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone

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The pentamethoxyflavone (II) has been synthesised by subjecting 5-hydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (VII) to hydroxylation with alkaline persulphate and subsequent methylation; it has been recently reported to occur in the orange peel and named sinensetin.

Gardenin (I) is an unusual type of flavonol derivative occurring in the gum of *Gardenia lucida*¹; it has a 5,6,8-trisubstitution pattern in the condensed benzene ring. Its synthesis is comparatively difficult and a convenient method has been worked out, using nuclear reduction and nuclear oxidation as important stages². All the members of the gardenin group have been synthesised³. Since the flavone analogues could also be expected to occur in Nature, their synthesis has been in progress as a part of the programme of this laboratory. In view of the recent isolation of *sinensetin* from the orange peel⁴, considered to have the constitution of 5,6,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (II), we are publishing the results of its synthesis.

The synthesis of the above flavone (II) started from 2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyacetophenone⁵ (III) which was veratrylated and the veratrylated ester (IV) was rearranged to ω -veratryl-2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (V) in presence of sodamide and subsequently cyclised with formic acid when 5,6,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (VI) was obtained in a satisfactory yield. It was partially demethylated with hydrochloric and acetic acids mixture to afford 5-hydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (VII). Hydroxylation in the 8-position was effected with alkaline persulphate. The resulting 5,8-dihydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (VIII) on methylation with dimethyl sulphate yielded 5,6,8,3',4'-

1. Balakrishna and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 91.
2. Abluwalia *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3988.
3. Balakrishna and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 260.
4. Swift, Abstracts American Chemical Society Meeting, September, 1961;
5. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 959,

pentamethoxyflavone (II) which has m.p. almost similar to that described for the natural sample of sinensetin.

The synthesis of 5,6,8-trisubstituted flavones is more easy as compared to that of the corresponding flavonols (gardenin). One of the chief difficulties in the case of gardenin is the preparation of 2-hydroxy- ω -5,6-trimethoxyacetophenone. Consequently a step of nuclear reduction is necessary in order to use a more easily available flavonol derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Veratryloxy-5,6-dimethoxyacetophenone (IV).—Veratryl chloride (12 g.) was added to a solution of 2-hydroxy-5,6-dimethoxyacetophenone⁵ (6 g.) and pyridine (6 ml) in benzene (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 30 mins. Water was added to dissolve the pyridinium hydrochloride and the ester formed was extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed successively with H₂SO₄ (dil.), water, sodium hydrogen carbonate, and water; it was

*The mixed melting point of the above synthetic sample with the natural sample of sinensetin, kindly sent by Dr. L. J. Swift, was considerably depressed and further the infrared spectra of the two samples were not identical, particularly in the finger-print region. Therefore sinensetin is not 5,6,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone. On our communicating this to Dr. Swift, he re-examined the question and now informs us that sinensetin agrees with 5,6,7,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone. The name may still be used for this pentamethoxyflavone which occurs in orange peels (R. Born, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 264).

dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated. The residue was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) and cooled to 0°C. A colorless solid (6 g.) separated. It was crystallised from ethanol as colorless, thick, rhombic plates, m.p. 140-42°; negative ferric reaction. (Found: C, 63.4; H, 6.0. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 63.3; H, 5.6%).

5,6,3',4'-Tetramethoxyflavone (VI).—The ester (IV) (6 g.) was suspended in dry toluene (200 ml), treated with powdered sodamide (10 g.), and heated on a boiling water bath for 8 hrs. The mixture was filtered and the residue added to ice and H_2SO_4 (dil.). The product was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate to remove any acid, and dried. After evaporation of the ether, the residue furnished the diketone (V) as an oily yellow liquid (5 g.) which gave a positive ferric reaction and did not crystallise. It (5g.) was directly used for cyclisation by heating with formic acid (100 ml) on a boiling water bath for 10 mins. and pouring into water (400 ml), when a yellow precipitate separated. It was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised first from ethyl acetate-light petroleum mixture and finally from ethanol, when the flavone (VI) was obtained as creamy prismatic needles, yield 2.5 g., m.p. 179-81°; negative ferric reaction. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 5.6. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.3%).

5-Hydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (VII).—The flavone (VI) (2.4 g.) was heated with acetic and hydrochloric acids mixture (4:1, 125 ml) on a boiling water bath for 2 hrs. It was diluted with ice-cold water and the solid collected. The flavone (VII) crystallised from ethanol as yellow prisms and needles, yield 2.0 g., m.p. 215-16°; green ferric reaction. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 65.8; H, 4.9%).

5,8-Dihydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (VIII).—The flavone (VII) (1g.) was dissolved in aqueous KOH (0.9g./20 ml) and pyridine (40 ml) and to the cooled and stirred solution (5-10°) was added aqueous potassium persulphate (1.5g./50 ml) during 1 hr. After leaving the solution overnight, it was extracted with ether to remove pyridine, acidified to Congo red, centrifuged, and extracted with ether again to remove the unchanged and side-reaction products. The clear aqueous solution was treated with sodium sulphite (1g.) and HCl (conc., 25 ml) and heated at 80° for 1 hr. The flavone (VIII) (100 mg.) was collected and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum mixture when it was obtained as yellow crystals, softening at 222° and melting at 230-31°; brown changing to deep brown ferric reaction. It dissolved in 5% alkali to a pinkish red solution, turning brown and finally yellow. (Found: C, 62.2; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7%).

5,6,8,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone (II).—The flavone (VIII) (100 mg.) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml) and refluxed with potassium carbonate (2 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.2 ml) until negative ferric reaction was obtained. Acetone was distilled and water added to the mixture. The flavone (II) crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles and prisms, m.p. 176-77°; sinonsetin⁴, m.p. 177-77.5°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 64.5; H, 5.4%).